

Quantification of Alignment Quality of Aligned Discontinuous Fibers using 2D-FFT (Fast Fourier Transform)

John J. Tierney, Alex Vanarelli, John Morris, Shridhar Yarlagadda, John W. Gillespie Jr.
Center for Composite Materials, University of Delaware, Newark DE 19716

Introduction

- Highly aligned discontinuous fiber composites developed at UD-CCM called TuFF (Tailorable Universal Feedstock for Forming) produces formable aerospace grade properties equivalent to continuous fiber composites.
- The manufacturing process creates a dry bed of aligned fibers at low areal weight that needs to be quantified for alignment quality
- 2D FFT (Fast Fourier Transform) creates a frequency domain representation of an image and can be used to observe order and orientation within the microstructure.
- This effort looks to enable in-line QA-QC measurement of fiber alignment using FFT light-transmission processed images.

FFT Processing of TuFF

Poorly Aligned TuFF material

Highly Aligned TuFF material

2D-FFT intensity spectrum indicates the overall alignment quality of the material based on the intensity and 'shape' of the frequency domain

FFT Theory

Definition

$$F(u, v) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x, y) e^{-j2\pi(ux+vy)} dx dy,$$

$$f(x, y) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} F(u, v) e^{j2\pi(ux+vy)} du dv$$

where u and v are spatial frequencies.

Also will write FT pairs as $f(x, y) \Leftrightarrow F(u, v)$.

- $F(u, v)$ is complex in general,

$$F(u, v) = F_R(u, v) + jF_I(u, v)$$

- $|F(u, v)|$ is the **magnitude** spectrum
- $\arctan(F_I(u, v)/F_R(u, v))$ is the **phase** angle spectrum.
- Conjugacy: $f^*(x, y) \Leftrightarrow F(-u, -v)$
- Symmetry: $f(x, y)$ is **even** if $f(x, y) = f(-x, -y)$

In-Line QA-QC Inspection Software

- LabVIEW based Software for real-time in-line alignment quantification
- Line profiles at different frequencies show alignment at different length scales from bulk to filament level based in image resolution
- Software captures entire production datasets for process repeatability and consistency

Post Processing Data

- Profiling the FFT image resolves alignment at multiple length scales based on image resolution

Statistical results for fiber alignment from single Image

Line	Size (um)	N. Amplitude	Angle	Stdev	P/O	Res
Line 1	293 um	0.26	89.05	2.43	18.26	498
Line 2	146 um	1.00	90.19	0.99	99.93	790
Line 3	98 um	0.63	90.10	1.30	68.01	341
Line 4	73 um	0.42	90.00	1.48	49.08	176
Line 5	59 um	0.36	90.00	1.49	47.76	142
Line 6	49 um	0.18	89.62	2.10	26.90	158
Line 7	42 um	0.12	89.62	2.05	21.04	709
Line 8	37 um	0.11	88.86	2.18	20.59	725
Line 9	33 um	0.06	90.00	2.75	13.49	288
Line 10	29 um	0.05	88.57	2.88	13.29	263
Line 11	27 um	0.05	87.81	3.29	12.86	231
Line 12						

TuFF Production Facility with Lightbox Image Capture Stations

Lightbox with High Speed Camera

Statistical Data Over Time

